

Self-Supervised Online Camera Calibration for Autonomous Driving Applications

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Abstract

Camera calibration is a critical step for accurate perception in autonomous vehicles. However, traditional calibration methods are often laborious and time-consuming, and require specialised data collection and careful tuning. This process must be repeated whenever the parameters of the camera change, which can be a frequent occurrence due to vibration, impacts or extreme temperatures. This paper proposes a novel deep learning framework for self-supervised camera calibration. The framework learns the intrinsic and extrinsic camera parameters from unlabeled driving data. This allows the framework to calibrate the camera in real time, without the need for any physical targets or special planar surfaces. This could cut the cost of re-calibration for both the manufacturer and consumer as the vehicle can re-calibrate itself over the lifetime of the vehicle, which also improves the accuracy and safety of the ADAS systems on the car.

Keywords: Camera Calibration, Self-Supervised Depth & Pose Estimation, Machine Vision

1 Introduction

There are two stages of camera calibration: intrinsic and extrinsic. Intrinsic calibration refers to the calibration of the camera's internal parameters, such as the focal length and principal point. Extrinsic calibration refers to the calibration of the camera's external parameters, such as its location and orientation in space. Traditionally, camera calibration is performed once in a laboratory setting using special calibration targets. This can be a time-consuming and expensive process, and the calibration results may not be accurate over time due to factors such as temperature changes, vibration, and wear and tear. In recent years, deep learning has opened new possibilities for camera calibration [Bogdan et al., 2018]. The advantage of Deep learning methods is that they can continually learn calibration over the lifetime of the vehicle, without the need for special calibration targets. This makes deep learning-based calibration methods more efficient as they stay up to date with the constantly changing camera parameters due to external factors

Hence, we propose a novel deep learning-based camera calibration method for autonomous vehicles. Our method is able to learn the intrinsic and extrinsic parameters of the camera from data collected while the vehicle is in motion. This allows for provide accurate calibration over the lifetime of the vehicle, without the need for manual intervention.

Traditional camera calibration methods require specialized lab settings and target patterns. Zhang's method [Zhang, 2000], is a popular traditional CV method that only requires a checkerboard pattern and can be done in any environment. The method works by detecting feature points in the checkerboard pattern under different orientations, which can be achieved by moving either the camera or the plane.

The proposed approach uses properties of Self supervised depth and pose estimation networks like [Guizilini et al., 2020] and [Godard et al., 2019] as proxy to also learn calibration. [Garg et al., 2016] first introduced the idea of the joint learning of depth and ego-motion. The proposed method provided a significant contribution to the subject of depth estimation as it allows for the learning of depth estimation from monocular images totally unsupervised.

2 Methodology

The proposed calibration framework uses self-supervised monocular depth and pose estimation as a proxy for learning camera calibration with the addition of a third network to learn intrinsics. Self-supervised depth and ego-motion architectures consist of a depth network that produces a depth map and a pose network that predicts the transformation between the current frame and the context frame. With this known transformation and depth map, one can warp/project the current frame into a target image and train the networks jointly by minimising the photometric loss between the actual image and the synthesised image from the projection. Monodepth2 [Godard et al., 2019] was chosen as a base framework for the project. Monodepth2 is a popular and well documented Pytorch-based self-supervised monocular depth estimation network. At the core of the project is a depth network with a multi-input ResNet [He et al., 2016] encoder and UNet [Ronneberger et al., 2015] decoder alongside a pose CNN, also with a multi-input ResNet encoder.

Figure 1: Calibration Framework Architecture

2.1 Architecture

The modified monodepth2 framework consists of:

- Depth network: ResNet-50 encoder pre-weighted on ImageNet & UNet decoder.
- Pose network: Multi-input ResNet-50 encoder pre-weighted on ImageNet & Pose CNN.
- Intrinsic network consists of 4 or more trainable parameters (Depending on the camera model) representing intrinsic camera parameters which feed into the view synthesis function for image warping.

(a) Intrinsic Network pseudo diagram

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{pmatrix} f_x & 0 & c_x \\ 0 & f_y & c_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

(b) Traditional Intrinsic matrix

2.1.1 Intrinsic Network

The intrinsic network consists of 4 or more trainable parameters (Depending on camera model) which represent the intrinsic parameters of the relevant camera model. The network takes two inputs, the camera model and the image shape. The network outputs a tensor of size 1x4 (depending on camera model). This tensor is then manipulated into a traditional 3x3 intrinsic matrix which is fed into the image warping function and the network is trained in simultaneously with the depth and pose network by minimising the photometric loss.

2.1.2 Data

The framework was trained on the KITTI dataset. The KITTI dataset is a benchmark dataset commonly used in computer vision for depth estimation. The Eigen zhou split was used which is a subset of the KITTI dataset which consists of 39K images for training and 4k images for validation. A further 679 unseen images are used for evaluation.

3 Experiments and Results

The framework is trained in a self-supervised manner by minimising photometric reconstruction error. The framework was trained for 20 Epochs with a learning rate of 0.0001 and a batch size of 4. Training took 36 hours on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080ti graphics card.

Model	Abs Rel \downarrow	Sq Rel \downarrow	RMSE \downarrow	RMSE log \downarrow
Base monodepth2	0.114	0.931	4.810	0.192
monodepth2 x IntrinsicNet	0.112	0.851	4.706	0.188

Table 1: Depth metric results vs baseline

Comparing the depth metrics of the baseline vs learned intrinsics is one way to evaluate the learned intrinsics in the absence of synthetic data as we are using depth estimation as a proxy to learn camera calibration. Comparing the two we see that the modified framework has a slight improvement in depth evaluation metrics, possibly due to the learned intrinsics being more accurate than the static KITTI parameters.

Model	Intrinsics	Abs Rel \downarrow	Sq Rel \downarrow	RMSE \downarrow
Gordon et al	K (P)	0.129	0.982	5.23
	L (P)	0.128	0.959	5.23
J. Fang et al	L (P)	0.129	0.8393	4.96
Monodepth2	K (P)	0.114	0.931	4.810
Monodepth2x IntrinsicNet	L (P)	0.112	0.851	4.70

Table 2: Depth metric results vs baseline

Table 4 shows a comparison of depth metrics from other camera based learning methods [Fang et al., 2022, Gordon et al., 2019] trained on the Eigen split of the KITTI dataset. K denotes known intrinsics and L denotes learned intrinsics. Note the proposed implementation is trained on the Eigen Zhou split which contains the same files but has extra data added from more challenging scenes and lower lighting. This means the Eigen Zhou split is more challenging and provides a better estimation of the model’s generalisation capability. The table provides a quick comparison of improved metrics between baseline and learned intrinsics of other implementations.

4 Conclusion & Future work

This paper proposes a novel self-supervised deep learning framework that learns camera calibration from unlabelled video input. As seen the framework learns calibration, which improved depth evaluation metrics by providing more accurate calibration parameters than the static calibration parameters provided in KITTI. As with any real world dataset the calibration provided does not represent the true parameters of the camera, only a very good estimate of the parameters at time of calibration.

Future work would be to train the framework on synthetic data. The advantage of using synthetic data is that we know the exact true calibration parameters of the camera so we can accurately evaluate the networks outputs. Other future work would be to adapt the framework to work with wider field of view camera models like the fisheye camera model.

In summary the proposed framework could potentially be very effective as a recalibration tool for vehicle perception systems and could cut the cost of recalibration for both manufacturer and consumer.

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